

PROSPECTS FOR THE USE OF LAYERED GASIFIERS USING ANGREN BROWN COAL

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Abstract: a review of coal gasification technologies in layer gasifiers is provided and the possibilities of obtaining generator gas of low and medium calorific value from Angren brown coal, the reserves of which are about 2 billion tons, are assessed. Foreign operating layer gasifiers for solid fuels are considered. The calorific, physicochemical characteristics of gases obtained from solid fuels are analyzed. The main factors that hinder the widespread use of gasification technologies for solid fuels are presented. Ways to solve technological problems to increase the efficiency of gas generators are considered.

Key words: gasification, coal, direct process, reverse process, ash, resins.

INTRODUCTION

The development of global energy in the 21st century shows that the bulk of electricity production still comes from hydrocarbons. The use of coal in the production of electrical and thermal energy as fuel remains an urgent task to this day. However, the widespread use of coal technologies in the production of electrical and thermal energy is hampered by a number of factors:

- high cost of technological equipment;
- air pollution;
- complexity of operation (processes of fuel preparation, combustion and ash removal);
- low efficiency;

- large overall dimensions.

Uzbekistan, as a country with large coal reserves, has great potential for the development of small coal power plants.

The total geological reserves of coal in the Republic of Uzbekistan amount to more than 4.8 billion tons, of which 1,832.8 million tons are explored. Brown coal reserves, located mainly in the Tashkent, Fergana, Navoi regions and Karakalpakstan, amount to 1,786.5 million tons. Coal reserves located in the southern regions of the republic - in the Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions - 46.3 million tons. Forecast coal resources - 323.4 million tons.

The organization OJSC Uzbekkumir carries out industrial development of the largest Angren lignite deposit in the Tashkent region, the explored coal reserves of which are 1.9 billion tons, and the predicted resources exceed 5.7 billion tons [1].

Angren coal belongs to the category of resinous brown coals - dense, dark brown, even black in color, with a shine like resin when broken.

A representative sample of fine coal from the Angren deposit, which, after drying to an air-dry state and grinding to a particle size of 0.25 mm, has the following composition (table 1.) [2]:

Table 1. Air-dry composition of Angren coal (weight, %).

Moisture, %	Ash, %	Organic, %	Humic acids, %
14.1	13.7	72.2	4.1

The working mass and lower calorific value of Angren brown coal are given in table 2 [3]:

Table 2. Characteristics of the working mass of Angren brown coal.

Moisture W^r , %	Ash content A^r , %	Carbon C^r , %	Sulfur $S_p^r + S_o^r$, %	Hydrogen H^r , %	Oxygen O^r , %	Nitrogen N^r , %	Lower calorific value Q_i^r , kcal/kg
34.5	14.4	39.1	1.3	1.9	8.6	0.2	3 210

The difficulties in developing coal gasification technologies in our country are due to:

- low quality coal;
- air pollution;
- lack of specific developed technologies, gasification installations for Angren coal;
- high cost of technological equipment;
- the possibility of using generator gas only for the production of electrical and thermal energy, etc.

Widespread implementation of coal gasification technologies is possible by solving the following problems:

- focus on local coals;
- minimal impact on the environment;
- ensuring increased efficiency of the process;
- the ability to operate equipment under variable loads while ensuring high performance.

Layer gasification of coal. Among all possible solid fuel gasification technologies, dense layer technology is the simplest from a technical point of view. There are several ways to supply gasifying agents relative to the fuel flow

[4-8]. The main ones are:

- direct blast supply, gasifying agent against the direction of fuel flow);
- reverse supply (in the direction of fuel flow);
- combined (in both directions);
- cross (in the perpendicular direction).

Direct gasification with a fixed bed. Layer gasification (Fig. 1.a) is one of the first and simplest methods for gasification of solid fuel. The fuel moves in the opposite direction to the gasifying agent (air) and the vapor-gas mixture formed in the process. The gasification process in layered gas generators takes place in four zones:

1. Oxidation zone. The solid fuel is oxidized by a gasifying agent. Air is supplied from below the oxidation zone through the grate. The grate ensures uniform distribution of air flow. Ash is removed through the holes of the grate. The combustion process of coke ash residue is accompanied by the following reactions [9-12]:

Fig.1. Main types of layer gas generators. a) direct process gas generator
b) reverse process gas generator.

Reactions (1) and (2) are accompanied by the formation of carbon monoxide during combustion of the carbon residue. The oxidation of fuel hydrogen occurs through heterogeneous and homogeneous processes in accordance with reactions (3) and (4). Reactions (1)–(5) are exothermic, and the temperature in the combustion zone can reach 1775-1975 K. A low level of mechanical underburning is ensured by intensive high-temperature conversion of the carbon residue.

2. Reduction zone. Above the combustion zone there is a reduction zone of CO_2 and H_2O , which is accompanied by the following reactions:

In the recovery zone, the layer temperature decreases due to heat absorption and radiation from the combustion zone. The formation of methane by reactions (9) and (10) at a noticeable rate is possible only at high pressures (2-4 MPa) in a gas generator.

3. Pyrolysis zone. The next stage of gasification is the pyrolysis zone. In this zone, the heat of the generator gas promotes the decomposition of the fuel with the formation of gas, tar and coal residue. In the pyrolysis zone, the gas is enriched with methane and C_2 hydrocarbons.

4. Drying zone. In the drying zone, working moisture is removed from the fuel. The temperature of the generator gas can be 450-670 K.

The relatively low outlet temperature distinguishes the direct process from other gasification processes. This makes it possible to achieve a high overall efficiency of the installation, which can reach 85% (Table 3).

Table 3. Main technical characteristics of layer-type gas generators

Gas generator type	Gas generator reverse process	Gas generator direct process
Fuel particle size, mm	20-100	5-100
Moisture, %	12-25	43-60
Ash, %	0.5-6	1.4-25
Combustible gas outlet temperature, K	975	475-675
Overall efficiency, %	65-76	70-85
Resin content in raw gas, g/m^3	0.015-0.5	30-150
Heat of combustion of gas, $Q_i, \text{kcal/m}^3$	1 075-1 120	1 310-1 430

Sensitivity to change in fuel supply	high	low
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The main disadvantages of the direct process are high resin yield, uneven shrinkage of the fuel and the formation of arches. Also, there are high heat losses through the grate, especially if there is no ash cushion on it.

The efficiency of the grate can be affected by slagging of the fuel, which forms at high temperatures.

In world practice, there are many successfully implemented pilot and operating direct-acting layered gas generators. Below are some of them [13,14].

American company Union Carbide has developed a technology for processing and producing fuel gas from municipal solid waste, thanks to which the developers were able to obtain gas with an average calorific value. This technology is called the Purox process. Pure oxygen is supplied as a gasifying agent for combustion. Thanks to the use of oxygen as a gasifying agent, it was possible to obtain a higher calorific value of fuel gas up to 2820-3680 kcal/nm³. The temperature of the generator gas at the outlet of the gas generator was 373...585 K. The resulting gas can be used in boiler furnaces, roasting and heating furnaces. High temperatures, reaching up to 1775 K, are a distinctive feature of the Purox process. Due to the increased temperature in the combustion zone, it is possible to carry out liquid slag removal.

Another successfully implemented direct process installation is the G-3 gas generator, designed for the Pologov oil extraction plant located in Ukraine. The use of finely dispersed raw materials to produce generator gas made it possible to obtain experimental data for fuel of a certain size. The main characteristics of the gas generator are given in table 4.

Table 4. Technical characteristics of the gas generator G-3

No.	Name of parameters and characteristics	Meaning
1	Rated thermal power for gas combustion, kW	5 000
2	Nominal gas capacity (dry), m ³ /h	3 200
3	Nominal consumption of husks at a humidity of 12%, kg/h	1 250
4	Heat of combustion of dry gas, kcal/m ³	1 410
5	Nominal air flow, m ³ /h	

	to tuyeres:	1 500
	on the grate:	500
6	Nominal steam consumption, m ³ / h	200
7	Working pressure in the shaft, kPa	1.5
8	Gas temperature at the gas generator outlet, K	625
9	Efficiency, %	92
10	Overall dimensions, (height × diameter), m	8.3x4.5
11	Weight of gas generator with lining, no more, t	21
12	Amount of residual product (ash, coke), kg/h	30

Converted layer gasification. Another common layer gasification method is the inverse method. The reverse supply of the gasifying agent is carried out in the direction of fuel movement (Fig. 1.b.). As in the direct gasification method, the inverse method consists of four reaction zones. The combustion zone is located below the pyrolysis and drying zone. In this regard, partial decomposition of the resulting resins under the influence of high temperatures is ensured. After the combustion zone, below is the recovery zone. Here, the combustion products of fuel and volatile to combustible gases with a small tar content are restored. The main disadvantage of the inverse method is the low efficiency of the installation due to fuel preparation. This disadvantage is due to the fact that in the reverse method there are restrictions on humidity and ash content of the fuel (raw materials). The choice of method for supplying blast in the reverse process depends on the power of the gas generator, as well as the size of the fuel particles and the porosity of the layer.

Along with the above basic methods of layered gasification, there are other gasification methods such as: a combined method, stepwise or multi-zone gasification [15].

In the combined method, blast is supplied from above and below into the fuel layer. In this case, a direct process takes place in the lower part of the layer, and a reverse process occurs in the upper part. Producer gas is removed at the border of the recovery zones. The instability of the operating mode of gas generators of this type complicates the gasification process.

A promising process for the conversion of solid fuels is multi-zone gasification. The process allows for deep decomposition of the resin in the gas generator itself. A number of existing technologies that implement a unified multi-zone process scheme are described in [16].

Antoine de Lacotte [17] developed and patented one of the first multi-zone gas generators in the 40s of the last century. Oxidative pyrolysis occurs in the upper part of the layered gas generator; gaseous products are taken from the above-layer space and sent to the external combustion chamber. The oxidized products of the tarred gas return to the middle of the fuel layer. One third of these products goes for recycling into the pyrolysis zone, and two thirds for gasification of semi-coke. The resulting generator gas is of high purity.

A gas generator design similar to de Lacotte was proposed and patented in 2008 by the Greek researcher Elefsiniotis [18]. Elefsiniotis installed an air supply to the oxidative pyrolysis zone in the gas generator shaft. With a similar improvement, the author was able to control the amount of gas that is recirculated from the combustion chamber.

The main disadvantage of de Lacotte and Elefsiniotis gas generators is the low chemical efficiency of gasification, the reason for which is high heat loss due to cooling of the external combustion chamber. The possibility of placing this chamber inside a fuel layer was considered in [19]. Instead of dissipating into the environment, the released heat is absorbed by the pyrolysis process.

Factors influencing the development of coal gasification technologies. The presence of some technological problems prevents the widespread use of gas generators in practice. The unsolved nature of these problems makes it difficult for gasification plants to compete with direct combustion plants. Several main technological problems can be identified that negatively affect the stability of the gasification process [20,21].

1. Instability of the combustion process. The organization of a stable combustion process depends on the continuous supply of fuel and blast to the gas

generator. In addition, it is important to ensure stable ignition of the fuel entering the combustion zone, as well as continuous removal of generator gas and ash.

2. Fuel sintering. Sintering of solid fuel (coal) occurs when the fuel transforms into a plastic state in the pyrolysis zone. The sintering of most coals is observed in the temperature range of 625-700 K, the solidification temperature is 780-790 K. The sintering of solid fuel ends in the range of 715-815 K. The main indicator of the sintering of coal is the release of volatiles into the combustible mass when the fuel is heated to 715 K and the higher indicator $\frac{C^r+H^r}{O^r}$. Sintering is not observed in brown coals, anthracites, lean and long-flame coals, as well as in peat. Sintering is accompanied by uneven shrinkage of the layer and mechanical underburning [22].

3. Resin formation during the conversion process. The release of resinous compounds negatively affects the internal surface and shut-off and control valves of gas generators. Hard-to-remove deposits appear inside the gas generator, and gas ducts are blocked [23]. Due to the formation of loose deposits, dust and soot from the generator gas, it is necessary to stop the gas generator for cleaning approximately once every 6-12 months.

4. Low efficiency of existing installations. Regardless of the type of structure, process conditions and type of fuel in gas generators, the gasification process is accompanied by a partial conversion of the chemical energy of the fuel into the chemical energy of gas, which reaches 50-70%. In this case, the physical heat of the gas is neglected.

The technological problems mentioned above are conditional in nature and are closely related to each other.

CONCLUSION

Research into coal gasification processes is an urgent task for the energy sector of Uzbekistan. Having great opportunities for the extraction of high-ash Angren coal, this topic becomes more attractive. At a time when our country's natural gas and oil reserves are used to ensure stability in electrical energy, the production of generator

gases with low and medium calorific values can solve a number of issues regarding the generation of thermal energy for technological and domestic needs. Technological improvement of existing and development of new gasification methods are current areas of modern scientific and technical research.

To achieve these goals, it is necessary to solve a number of problems that the authors are working on, namely:

- determination of optimal parameters for stable management of the gasification process;

-reducing the level of negative impact on the environment;

-increasing the efficiency and safety level of process equipment;

Solving technological problems will increase the level of commercialization and competitiveness of gasification.

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